

Pre-biopsy Multi-Class Classification of Breast Lesion Pathology in Mammograms

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Abstract. Characterization of lesions by artificial intelligence (AI) has been the subject of extensive research. In recent years, many studies demonstrated the ability of convolution neural networks (CNNs) to successfully distinguish between malignant and benign breast lesions in mammography (MG) images. However, to date, no study has assessed the specific sub-type of lesions in MG images, as detailed in histopathology reports. We present a method for finer classification of breast lesions in MG images into multiple pathology sub-types. Our approach works well with radiologists' diagnostic workflow, and uses data available in radiology reports. The proposed Dual-Radiology Dual-Resolution Network (Du-Rad Du-Res Net) receives dual input from the radiologist and dual image resolutions. The radiologist input includes annotation of the lesion area and semantic radiology features; the dual image resolutions comprise a low resolution of the entire mammogram and a high resolution of the lesion area. The network estimates the likelihood of malignancy, as well as the associated pathological sub-type. We show that the combined input of the lesion region of interest (ROI) and the entire mammogram is important for optimizing the model's performance. We tested the AI in a reader study on a dataset of 100 heldout cases. The AI outperformed three breast radiologists in the task of lesion histopathology sub-typing.

Keywords: Breast cancer · Mammography · Deep neural networks

1 Introduction

Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women, accounting for 30% of female cancers in the United States in 2020 [1]. Breast cancer detection commonly starts with a breast mammography (MG), which is currently the main imaging modality used for breast cancer screening. Following an examination of MG images and additional clinical information by a radiologist, approximately 10% of screening patients are recalled for further imaging examinations [2–4]. Among the recalled patients, about 10% will undergo needle biopsy due to suspicious abnormal findings [4]. However, the majority of these biopsies are ultimately classified as having a non-malignant pathology. Only 10 to 30% of breast biopsies were classified as malignant in the USA [5], thus there is a significant opportunity to reduce those that turn out to have been unnecessary. In addition to malignant/non-malignant classification, suspicious lesions in histology images are further classified to more subtle sub-categories ranging from benign tumors to invasive cancers. In this study, we focus on predicting a finer sub-typing of breast histopathology.

The correlation between the appearance of lesions in MG images and their histology sub-typing has been the subject of several works. Histology sub-categories often contain special or unique characteristics that can be found inside the MG images. For example, Holland and Hendriks [6] present a tight correlation between micro-calcification appearance and characterization in MG, and their appearance in histology images, for different ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) sub-types. Other works suggest a correlation between the tumor size, tumor margin, and tumor shape that appear in the MG to the specific histology sub-type [7]. A detailed review of additional works that study the connection between MG and histology images can be found in [8].

The proliferation in AI-based medical diagnostics has led to extensive research in the field of lesion classification in MG exams. The most common approach is to classify the entire mammogram image into two coarse categories of “malignant” versus “non-malignant” using a convolution neural network (CNN) [9–13]. Another approach is to identify “normal” images without any lesion, to reduce the screening workload of the radiologist [14–18]. To the best of our knowledge, there is no previous study on classifying lesions in MG images into finer histopathological sub-types. AI systems typically process MG images in lower resolution, since the

actual size of a mammogram image is too large for the memory of standard computers. Several studies demonstrated improved accuracy for classifiers trained on full resolution image patches of ROIs extracted by lesion annotations [11–13]. In a recent work [19], Shen et al. present a novel method for using both the full image, and the suspicious lesions that are extracted in a weakly-supervised manner, to predict the presence or absence of benign and malignant lesions in a breast.

This paper presents a novel CNN multi-class architecture for the task of predicting lesion histopathology sub-types in MG images. Our study builds on information available in radiologists’ reports: (i) annotations of suspicious areas, and (ii) semantic features, such as lesion size and type (e.g., mass, calcification). We evaluated our model on a heldout dataset and in a reader study conducted with three specialized breast-imaging radiologists.

2 Methods

2.1 Dataset

We used an in-house dataset of MG images with local annotations of visible suspected findings. This dataset was collected from 4 different sites and multiple imaging machines in the United States. In all, the dataset covers 2860 unique patients that were sent for biopsy. Each case includes 1 or more images from screening and diagnostic studies. All known pathology diseases can be grouped into categories according to their further management in clinical work- up: malignant, benign, and benign with risk. We further split the malignant category into DCIS and invasive sub-groups, and the benign with risk category into lesions with atypia (lifetime high-risk) and benign pathologies associated with pre-malignant tumors (e.g., papilloma). Given that, data labels including pathology-based sub-categories were grouped into five major categories: DCIS, invasive, papilloma, high risk and benign lesions. A table of diseases and classes is displayed in the Supplementary material. Images with more than one class were assigned multiple class labels.

We randomly split the data into training, validation, and test sets, while ensuring no patient overlap between the three. The random partition was made in a stratified manner to preserve the frequency of the five classes in each of the three data sets. Statistics on the number of images and lesions appear in Table 1. All images contain local annotations of the biopsied lesions, including contour around the lesion, pathology label, and semantic features extracted from the radiologist’s report. These features were extracted using basic text processing techniques and include lesion size, lesion type (i.e., mass, calcification), shape (oval, round, irregular), margins (circumscribed, spiculated), and appearance of suspicious structures (e.g., grouped microcalcification or architectural distortion).

For weights initialization, we used a large dataset of globally labeled images and pre-trained the backbone of the network on the related task of classifying an MG image into normal/benign/malignant. This globally annotated dataset, which totaled 6341 benign, 5341 malignant, and 10507 normal images, was assembled by augmenting our in-house dataset (after excluding validation and heldout sets) with data from the OPTIMAM [20] database and a second in-house dataset.

Table 1. Data statistics: number of images; number of lesions.

	DCIS	Invasive	High-risk	Papilloma	Benign	Total
Train	476; 539	1060; 1238	155; 192	228; 263	2398; 2735	4317; 4967
Validation	104; 110	227; 245	31; 41	50; 56	487; 574	899; 1026
Heldout	105; 113	234; 269	29; 39	45; 62	523; 586	936; 1069
Reader-study	22; 22	24; 25	7; 9	16; 20	29; 30	98; 106

2.2 Proposed Method

In this work, we used both the full image and patches of the lesion ROI. Thus, the algorithm received the context low-resolution (low-res) information that may affect the finding’s classification and the fine-detailed high-resolution (high-res) information from the lesion area. To extract the patches, we cropped the lesion area with margins of 60 pixels and resized all patches to the same size of 512 × 512. The alternative of

cropping patches of the same size could possibly crop out information in larger lesions. The other alternative of cropping different patches from the lesion’s ROI and aggregating the results would be very noisy. The full images were cropped around the breast area and resized to 2200×1200 while maintaining the aspect ratio. These images were then zero-padded to a final size of 2260×1260 . As a final step, the obtained images were normalized to $[0;1]$.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Du-Rad Du-Res Network. The architecture contains low-res and high-res sub-networks, with Seg. branch for the former. Additionally it contains a third dual-res sub-network in which patch and full image representations from the two other sub-networks are concatenated to create a dual-res representation. A fully convolutional classification head is applied to each of the sub-networks to compute multi-class predictions. A fourth sub-network, uses two fully connected layers for the semantic radiology features, and is concatenated to the input for the sub-network classification heads.

Figure 1 depicts our Du-Rad Du-Res Net. Our proposed model architecture receives dual input from the radiologist: (i) annotation of the lesion area and (ii) semantic features describing the lesion’s visual characterizations. The model also receives the dual-resolution images: (i) a low-res full image and (ii) a high-res patch. These inputs are processed by 3 inter-connected networks, that do not share weights: full image network, patch network, and semantic features network. We used the well-known InceptionResnet-V2 (IRV2) architecture [21] as a baseline model and as a backbone for both the full image and patch networks. We optimized the model for small datasets by cutting the network off after 14 IRV2 blocks, before the global max pooling (GMP) layer. The semantic features network consisted of 2 (FC) layers with 64 and 384 neurons, respectively. Our model creates features that encapsulate information from both the full and patch images. First, the $[H, W, C]$ features from the patch network are concatenated to the $[H, W, C]$ features from the full image network. This is done after the features from the patch network were duplicated to fit the dimensions of the full image network. Then, a 3×3 convolution layer is applied to the resulting $[H, W, C]$ features, leading to $[H, W, C]$ features of mixed resolutions. The features corresponding to the full image, patch, and mixed resolutions are then concatenated with the output features from the semantic features network, producing features of size $[2H, W, C]$, where $H = 384$, $W = 139$, $C = 77$. Our model has 3 main classification branches corresponding to the 3 feature types described above: low-res full image, high-res patch, and dual-res full-image-patch mixture. These branches share the same architecture, which is a GMP layer followed by 5 classification sub-branches, each having a single hidden layer of 256 neurons. Thus, overall, our model produces 15 prediction scores. In addition, we follow Ness et al. [22] and add a Seg. branch to the full image network before the global pooling, using a binary segmentation map of the lesion as ground truth. The final loss is a combination of cross-entropy for each of the 3 branches (multi-resolution, or MR) per class (multi-class, or MC) predicting a one vs. all probability and the segmentation branch loss (seg):

$$L_{MC-MR} = \sum_{i \in C_{1,\dots,5}} (L_{LR,i} + L_{HR,i} + L_{DR,i}) + \lambda L_{seg},$$

where λ was set to 2 after some hyper parameter tuning on the validation set, and $C_{1,\dots,5}$ are the 5 sub-typing classes.

2.3 Model Training

We trained the models for 100 epochs using NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs, PyTorch, and FuseMedML framework [23]. Each minibatch consisted of 2 images, 1 from malignant classes and 1 from benign classes. We initialized the weights of the full image and patch branches using our pretrained network as mentioned in 2.1. We then fine-tuned the entire network. For data augmentation, applied to both patches and full images, we used random rotation and translation, flipping, and zooming. In addition, we applied color augmentations of contrast, gamma, and intensity. We used Adam optimizer, with an initial learning rate of 10^{-4} .

3 Experiments and Results

We evaluated our Du-Res-Du-Rad model on the 1069 image-lesion pairs in our heldout dataset (see Table 1). We set the predicted class of the model as the class with the highest predicted score. Table 2 presents the accuracy of the model’s predicted class and the ROC curve (AUC) per class. As shown, the invasive classification had the highest AUC (0.85 [95% CI 0.82,0.87]), while accuracy was highest for the benign category (0.83 [95% CI 0.76, 0.83]). Note that benign and invasive are our largest classes, and also those found at the two extremes of the sub-categories’ spectrum.

Ablation Study. To evaluate the contribution of the different components in our Du-Rad Du-Res Net model, we tested four incremental model variants: testing the contribution of the segmentation branch, dual-res architecture, model pre-training, and semantic features to our model performance. The results of this ablation study are presented in Table 2, where models with the Du-Res component are presented with three AUCs corresponding to the low-res, high-res, and dual-res classification heads. As shown, the addition of each tested component incrementally improves the overall performance of the classification heads. This indicates the importance of these components to the overall performance of our model. For all models, adding the low-res and high-res heads contributed to the model performance due to the regularization effect in training. For variants with dual-res architecture, the model prediction is done by the dual-res head.

Table 2. Du-Rad Du-Res Net model performance: accuracy of predicted class, and a comparison of AUC with simpler model variants.

Model	seg	pre-trained	low-res	high-res	dual-res	DCIS	Invasive	High-risk	Papilloma	Benign
IRV2			X			0.55	0.68	0.58	0.56	0.66
+Seg	X		X			0.72	0.72	0.55	0.62	0.69
+Du-Res	X		X			0.71	0.72	0.53	0.62	0.69
	X			X		0.75	0.80	0.56	0.59	0.73
	X				X	0.77	0.79	0.60	0.69	0.74
+Pre-trained	X	X	X			0.72	0.80	0.59	0.62	0.77
	X	X		X		0.76	0.81	0.58	0.55	0.76
	X	X			X	0.73	0.83	0.62	0.69	0.78
+Du-Rad [Du-Rad Du-Res]	X	X	X			0.80	0.83	0.67	0.67	0.77
	X	X		X		0.80	0.84	0.65	0.62	0.76
	X	X			X	0.78	0.85	0.69	0.72	0.78
Accuracy	X	X			X	0.37	0.64	0.21	0.02	0.83

Malignant vs. Benign Classification. Using the softmax function, we transformed a multi-class classifier, for the finer histopathology sub-types into a binary classifier for malignant vs. benign. We computed the malignancy score as the sum of the predicted scores for the DCIS and invasive subtypes. The significance of the results, was tested with DeLong test. With this transformation, our Du-Rad Du-Res Net model achieved an AUC of 0.816 [95% CI 0.789, 0.842] in the task of malignant vs. benign classification. As a baseline classifier, we used our low-res head, modified for binary classification, and trained it with the coarse malignant vs. benign labels. Compared to our model, this baseline had a significantly lower AUC of 0.71 [95% CI 0.68, 0.74] ($P \ll 0.0001$).

To evaluate the net contribution of finer sub-type labels to the binary classification of malignant vs. benign, we compared this baseline model (i.e., the low-res binary classification head) to the multi-class version of this model trained with the finer sub-types (i.e., the original low-res multi-class classification head). The AUC of the latter model showed an improved AUC of 0.73 [95% CI 0.69,0.76] ($P < 0.05$). The results imply that malignant classification can be improved by incorporating additional information from pathology reports. Finally, we explored the ability of our model to reduce the number of unnecessary biopsies. This can be especially useful in other body organs where the biopsy procedure is risky. The results presented in Table 3 show that the model could potentially assist in preventing 19% of the unnecessary biopsies, while missing 1% of the malignant cases.

Table 3. Du-Rad Du-Res Net model specificity at sensitivity levels for the task of malignant/benign.

Sensitivity	Specificity	95% CI for Specificity
0.99	0.19	[0.06, 0.21]
0.98	0.24	[0.11, 0.26]
0.95	0.38	[0.23, 0.38]

Reader Study. The reader study was conducted by three specialists in breast-imaging radiology, each with 15 to 30 years of experience, all from different organizations. Each radiologist viewed 100 images of the heldout set. The images were selected randomly, with no more than a single image per study. Two of the cases were disqualified by the readers due to poor quality; (see Table 1). As a first step, each radiologist viewed the low-res full image; and was then asked to predict the probability of malignancy. In addition, the radiologist was asked to assign it to one of the 5 sub-classes. Next, the radiologist repeated the process after being given both the full image and the lesion’s ROI. For the task of malignancy prediction, The AI outperformed the radiologists with an AUC of 0.75, compared to 0.68, 0.69, and 0.71 AUC for the readers. The significance of the results was tested with Wilcoxon signed-rank test. The improved results were found significantly only for Rad 1 ($P = 0.03$). The AI outperformed all 3 breast radiologists in the task of lesion histopathology sub-typing, with an accuracy of 45% compared to 28%,35% and 43% accuracy for the readers (detailed results in the Supplementary material). Here too, the improved results were found significant only when compared to Rad 1. Comparing the AI and radiologists’ performance of low-res versus dual-res, similar trends can be observed. For the benign class, we found that exposure to high-res impairs the results, giving us an average accuracy of 48% versus 64% for the low-res ($P < 0.0003$). In contrast, when we compared the performance for the invasive class, the accuracy in the dual-res scenario improved, from 59% to 67% when moving from low to high resolution. We measured the agreement between the readers and the AI model, and between pairs of readers, by calculating Cohen’s Kappa [24] scores. For the malignancy prediction, the average agreement between the readers and between the AI and the readers was low (Cohen’s Kappa of 0.31 [0.28–0.34] and 0.17 [0.08–0.25]). For the subtyping task, the level of agreement between radiologists was moderate (0.47 [0.4–0.56]). The agreement with the AI system was similar (0.45 [0.40–0.5]). Comparing the agreement between the two types of tasks, the agreement of the latter is higher due to a greater increase in the number of cases for which both are incorrect. Most of the disagreement between the readers and the AI was in the benign classes, which contain the hardest cases to analyze.

4 Discussion

In the United States each year, more than 1 million women undergo breast biopsy, yet, on average, approximately 80% yield benign findings. When combined with the anxiety, discomfort, cost, and potential complications of even minimally invasive fine needle biopsies, it is apparent that more accurate distinction of the lesions can have enormous clinical significance. Although biopsy is effective in cancer diagnosis, adding another modality to the diagnostic process could help radiologists offer more accurate diagnoses. In addition, the feasibility in breast MG could pave the way for additional imaging modalities and other body organs, where biopsy may be more risky or impractical. A large number of works, presented impressive results on the task of malignant versus benign lesions classification in MG. However, to the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to use a dual-radiology dual-resolution network to classify lesions into pathologic sub-types, which is more challenging due to the fine differences between the sub-classes. Although further work is needed, these

encouraging results offer additional supporting evidence that AI can improve the accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity of breast cancer diagnosis.

Waugh et al. [26], show the feasibility of differentiating between breast cancer sub-types by texture features from MRI. Our work differs from their work in four aspects: (i) We use the MG, which is the most common screening modality so no other imaging procedures need be applied. (ii) We perform finer sub-typing classification of malignant lesions as well as benign lesions. (iii) We use features that are extracted from both the full image, the ROI and the clinical report. (iv) The relatively large dataset allows us to use deep learning. We note that there is a limitation associated with our reader study since the radiologists are trained to predict malignancy and not the sub-typing. Hence, we compare AI and readers' performance in two tasks: malignancy prediction and sub-type classification.

The ground truth labels used in this study are based on pathological observations that may be noisy. Studies show that this categorization is often subjective and prone to observer variability [27]. Moreover, specifically for the DCIS category, a poor accuracy rate of only 65% was achieved in the core biopsy procedure [28]. In addition, a study published in JAMA in 2015 [25], showed that while pathologists have high concordance (96%) in diagnosing invasive carcinoma for needle biopsies, the agreement among pathologists was only 48% for atypical hyperplasia. It is possible that histology classification can also be improved by analyzing additional modalities, such as MG. This is a direction for future research work. In addition, we based our method on annotations given by the radiologists. Future work will focus on replacing this input with machine-computed parameters, as previous works have shown large accuracy in predicting them [19].

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Pre-biopsy multi-class classification of breast lesion pathology in mammograms - Supplementary

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Table 1. Pathology Sub Group Diseases.

Pathology	Pathology Sub Type	List of pathology diseases
Malignant	DCIS	Ductal Carcinoma In Situ
	Invasive	Invasive Ductal Carcinoma, Invasive Lobular Carcinoma, Invasive Mammary Carcinoma, Invasive Ductal Carcinoma Multicentric, Low-grade Serous Carcinoma, Mucinous Carcinoma, Papillary Carcinoma, Squamous Cell Carcinoma, Tubular Carcinoma
Benign	High Risk	Atypia , Atypical Ductal Hyperplasia, Atypical Lobular Hyperplasia, Lobular Carcinoma in Situ of Breast
	Papilloma	Intraductal Papilloma, Papilloma, Papillomatosis, Phyllodes Tumor, Radial Scar, Sclerosing Papilloma
	Benign	Angiolipoma, Angiomatosis, Apocrine Metaplasia, Benign Breast Tissue, Cyst, Dense Stromal Fibrosis, Ductal Adenoma, Edema, Fat Necrosis, Fibroadenoma, Fibroadenolipoma, Fibrocystic Change, Fibromatosis, Fibrosing Adenosis, Fibrosis, Granuloma, Granular Cell Tumor, Gynecomastia, Hematoma, Lactating Adenoma, Lipoma, Lymphoid Hyperplasia, Mastitis, Myofibroblastoma, Mammary Duct Ectasia, Neoplasm of Skin of Breast, Plasma Cell Mastitis, Pseudoangiomatous Stromal Hyperplasia, Reactive Lymph Node, Sclerosing Adenosis, Seborrhoeic Keratosis, Sebaceous Cyst of Skin of Breast, Seroma, Usual Ductal Hyperplasia

Fig. 1. Examples for the five sub-types. A-DCIS, B-Invasive, C-High Risk, D-Papilloma, E-Benign

Fig. 2. Cases of AI and readers conflicts. A-DCIS case. AI and Rad 1 correctly predicted both malignancy and sub-type, whereas Rad 2-3 diagnosed as Invasive. B-DCIS case predicted correctly only by AI. All readers incorrectly diagnosed this as Benign (Rad 1 as Benign High Risk and Rad 2-3 as Benign) due to benign type classification. C-Benign case correctly predicted by both AI and Rad 2-3, though incorrectly diagnosed as Benign High Risk by Rad 1 due to suspicious calcifications. D-DCIS case predicted correctly only by AI. Rad 1 correctly diagnosed it as malignant, but was wrong about the sub-type, whereas Rad 2-3 diagnosed it as Benign.

Table 2. Our model (AI) and readers performance in the reader study. TP = true positives. FN = false negatives.

Model	Measure	Low-res	Dual-res	DCIS	Invasive	High Risk	Papilloma	Benign
AI	TP	✓		5	12	0	0	22
	FN		✓	8	17	0	0	20
			✓	17	13	9	20	8
			✓	14	8	9	20	10
Reader 1	TP	✓		8	16	2	0	14
	FN		✓	5	16	0	0	7
			✓	14	9	7	20	16
			✓	17	9	9	20	23
Reader 2	TP	✓		4	15	0	0	21
	FN		✓	5	16	0	0	14
			✓	18	10	9	20	9
			✓	17	9	9	20	16
Reader 3	TP	✓		4	16	0	0	20
	FN		✓	8	18	0	0	17
			✓	18	9	9	20	10
			✓	14	7	9	20	13